

THE INTERPRETATION OF AMIR TEMUR'S LIFE AND STATECRAFT IN THE WORKS OF THE GERMAN HISTORIAN JOHANN CHRISTOPH GATTERER.

Nizomitdinov Doniyorjon Jaloldin o'g'li

Researcher at Fergana State University

donyornizomitdinov@gmail.com

ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5181-1673>

Tel: +998994994966

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20698630>

Abstract: This thesis discusses Johann Christoph Gatterer, who is recognized in eighteenth-century German historiography for his innovative methodological approaches, as well as his scholarly activity. In addition, the study analyzes Gatterer's research on the life and state-building activities of Amir Timur and examines his interpretations and views on the historical figure of Sahibqiran

Keywords: Enlightenment ideas, eighteenth-century German historiography, Göttingen Historical Institute, Johann Christoph Gatterer, Linnaeismus graphicus, Gatterer's works, the conceptual understanding of the names "Timur" and "Tamerlane".

The German school of historiography occupies a distinctive place among the historiographical traditions of the world. It would not be an exaggeration to state that many of the methods developed within German historiography have served as models for historical scholarship worldwide. During the eighteenth century, the ideas of the Enlightenment (*Aufklärung*) prevailed in Germany. German historiography likewise developed under the influence of Enlightenment thought. In this period, history gradually ceased to be merely a narrative recounting events and began to emerge as a scientific discipline focused on the verification of sources, critical analysis, and the explanation of historical development. German historians sought to study history not through religious narratives, but through evidence, sources, documents, and rational analysis. These developments are closely associated with the German historian Johann Christoph Gatterer, who laid the foundations for one of the earliest scholarly institutions dedicated to historical research in Germany. In 1759, Gatterer was appointed Professor of History at University of Göttingen. In 1764, he established the "Historical Academy" in Göttingen, and in 1766 he founded the "Historical Institute" for the publication of medieval historical sources. Gatterer believed that history should be presented "in its entirety" (*im ganzen Umfange*), emphasizing a comprehensive approach to historical study and representation [1].

Gatterer developed the concept of specialization in statistics and authored textbooks on chronology, numismatics, genealogy, geography, and general history. His manuals on heraldry, genealogy, geography, and general history served as standard reference works for a long period and continued to be used in education throughout the nineteenth century. Gatterer is widely regarded as a scholar who pioneered the scientific development of the auxiliary sciences of history. He also introduced innovative methods for the study of history. While developing new approaches to source analysis, Gatterer sought to systematize the evolution of writing by applying methods derived from botany. To achieve this, he created an approach known as “graphic Linnaeanism” (Linnaeismus graphicus)¹. Through this method, Gatterer aimed to determine the age of historical documents by classifying and comparing the forms and development of scripts in a systematic manner [2].

The institute founded by Gatterer represented a hybrid structure that combined the features of an academy and a university institute. It integrated historical education with historical research and later evolved into one of the earliest forms of the modern academic seminar. Two scholarly journals emerged from this institute: Allgemeine historische Bibliothek (General Historical Library) and Historisches Journal (Historical Journal). This institution is regarded as one of the first scientific research institutes in the field of history [3].

Martin Gierl notes that Gatterer’s principal contribution lay in the systematic integration of the scientific problems and achievements of his era into historiography [4]. Gatterer developed new methods for assessing the reliability of historical sources and for conducting their critical analysis. His approach was based on an information system that functioned through the interrelationship between oral and written evidence and their connection with the material remains of the past. Furthermore, he demonstrated that this system itself had been shaped by the various media and techniques employed in the preservation, transmission, and reproduction of historical evidence. Through this perspective, Gatterer sought to establish a more comprehensive and methodologically rigorous foundation for historical research.

Gatterer also acquired profound expertise in Oriental studies. He authored works on Universal History, in which he devoted particular attention to the history of the East, including the personality of Amir Temur and his state-building activities. In his studies of Amir Temur’s life, Gatterer relied primarily on

¹ Linnaeismus graphicus (grafik linnechilik) - A method that examines historical or social processes through their successive stages of development and transformation over time.

historical sources, notably the works of Sharaf ad-Din Ali Yazdi, Ibn Arabshah, French authors, and various Orientalist translations. In eighteenth-century German historical literature, Amir Temur was commonly referred to as “Tamerlane” or “Timur Lenk.” In the works of Johann Christoph Gatterer, the name “Timur” was used alongside “Tamerlane”; however, the designation “Timur” appeared first and occupied a primary position. The use of the name “Timur” in Gatterer’s writings reflects a broader tendency within eighteenth-century German historiography toward greater terminological authenticity in the naming of Eastern rulers. This tendency contributed to the gradual incorporation of the designation “Timur” into scholarly discourse and influenced subsequent historical research. This observation gives rise to the hypothesis that Gatterer employed “Timur” as the principal designation, while using “Tamerlane” as the more familiar European variant. As one of the historians who preferred the form “Timur,” which was closer to its usage in Eastern sources, he contributed to a terminological shift within later German historiography. During the eighteenth century, the Göttingen School of Historiography, under Gatterer’s leadership, created favorable conditions for the scholarly use of the name “Timur” alongside “Tamerlane.” As a result, German historians increasingly referred to Eastern rulers not by their traditional Europeanized names but by forms that more closely reflected their original names. This development also transformed the naming paradigm applied to Amir Temur within German historiography.

Johann Christoph Gatterer wrote the Handbook of Universal History in 1764. In this work, he attempted to classify the sources that provide information about history in America, Asia, Africa, and Europe. He also included in the work sources that provide information about the history of Amir Temur. He was the first to mention Ibn Arabshah’s work entitled Information about the Wonders of Fate in the Life and Activities of Timur, and he emphasized that Ibn Arabshah did not portray Amir Temur very positively [5]. He also provided information about the translation of the work into French and Latin.

Gatterer then provides information about Sharaf ad-Din Ali Yazdi’s Zafarnama. According to him, the work describes Amir Temur’s actions and campaigns in a very precise, detailed, and elegant manner. He also discusses the translation of this work into French and Turkish.

Gatterer also mentions that the German historian Johann Heinrich Boecler had written a book about Amir Temur entitled Tamerlanes. In addition, he provides information about French authors who wrote about Sahibqiran. From

this, it can be understood that Gatterer's knowledge of Amir Temur was formed mainly through works written in French and Latin.

Gatterer revised and republished his General History in 1773. In this work, he provides information about Amir Temur's rise to power, his military campaigns, and his system of state administration. Concerning Amir Temur's origin, the author records the incorrect information that he was a close relative of Genghis Khan. He describes Amir Temur as a conqueror who devastated the world, while at the same time portraying him as a zealous and just Muslim ruler [6].

He writes that Amir Temur formed an alliance with Amir Husayn, that they fought together against the Mongols, eventually drove away Ilyas Khoja, and elevated Kabul Shah to the position of khan. He also states that Amir Temur became a ruler in 1369 and that thereafter he received the title "Sahibqiran." At this point, it can be observed that the author presents contradictory information.

Gatterer notes that after seizing power, Amir Temur placed descendants of Genghis Khan on the throne as rulers. He compares this situation to the practice of Charles Martel and the Carolingians, who maintained puppet kings from the Merovingian dynasty, a phenomenon that he refers to as "theater kings." Gatterer describes each of Sahibqiran's major battles and writes that, before launching his campaign against China, he received the Spanish ambassador.

In 1792, Gatterer wrote one of his major works entitled Description of General World History. In this work, he sets forth his views on Amir Temur. He discusses Sahibqiran's campaigns in the Near East, his campaign in Asia Minor, and his campaigns along the Volga River, and presents his views regarding the alliance agreements concluded with Constantinople.

Gatterer notes that although Amir Temur's vast empire had disintegrated, the state that he had established continued to rule in India under the leadership of Babur for many years and was still in existence in the eighteenth century [7]. This indicates that, in eighteenth-century German historiography, the Timurid Empire was perceived as a continuous historical tradition.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Johann Christoph Gatterer introduced important innovations into the field of history through his research. As a result of his studies, numerous scholarly conclusions were incorporated into historiography. He sought to present history in a comprehensive manner. Among many historical figures, Gatterer devoted particular attention in his scholarly works to the personality of Amir Temur and his activities.

It can be observed that he approached Sahibqiran from two different perspectives. On the one hand, he portrayed Amir Temur as a great political and military leader and as the founder of a vast state. On the other hand, he described him as a destructive and conquering ruler..

List of sources and references:

1. Martin Gierl. Fundamenta Historika. Geschichte als Präzisierte Wissenschaft. Johann Christoph Gatterer und die Historiographie des. Jahrhundertsts im ganzen Umfang. – Stuttgart-Bad Cannstatt. 2012. – S. 1.
2. www.bwg.wiley-vch.de. André de Melo Araújo. Evidentiary Authority as a System: Johann Christoph Gatterer and the Collective Making of Historical Knowledge in the Eighteenth Century. doi.org/10.1002/bewi.2145. – S. 204
3. <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/sfz19997.html#ndbcontent>
4. Martin Gierl. Fundamenta Historika. Geschichte als Präzisierte Wissenschaft. Johann Christoph Gatterer und die Historiographie des. Jahrhundertsts im ganzen Umfang. – Stuttgart-Bad Cannstatt. 2012. – S. 2.
5. Johann Christoph Gatterers. Handbuch der Universalhistorie. nach ihrem gesamten Umfange bis auf unsere Zeiten fortgesetzt. des zweyten Theils erster Band. Nebst einer vorläufigen Einleitung, worin das Verzeichnis der Geschichtschreiber bis auf die neuern Zeiten fortgeführt worden. Göttingen im Verlag der Wittve Vandenhoeck, 1764. 432 s.
6. Johann Christoph Gatterers Abriss der Universalhistorie in ihrem ganzen Umfange. Bei dieser zwoten Ausgabe völlig umgearbeitet und bis auf unsere Zeiten fortgesetzt. Göttingen, im Verlag der Wittve Vandenhock. 1773. – S. 744 - 747.
7. Johann Christoph Gatterers. Versuch einer allgemeinen Weltgeschichte bis zur Entdeckung Amerikens. Göttingen, im Verlag Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht. 1792. – S. 835 – 838..